

QUALITY ASSESSMENT OF RAW AND DRINKING WATERS OF TIGRIS AND LOWER AL-ZAB RIVERS IN A SELECTED SECTOR OF KIRKUK AND SALAHALDEEN PROVINCES OF IRAQ

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ABSTRACT

Background: The natural bodies of freshwaters like rivers, lakes and springs are always under pressure of biological, chemical and physical pollutions. Nowadays, it can be added that different types of wars which have an impact on the natural environment lead to changes of distribution of various types of fauna and flora. **Methodology and Results:** The different water samples from River Tigris and lower Al-Zab river were tested for microbiological indicators of pollution as well as for analysis of chemical and physical parameters like air and water temperature, turbidity, dissolved oxygen, biological oxygen demand, pH and electrical conductivity. The highest degree of water pollution was seen during January of the year. **Conclusions:** The highest degree of water pollution was seen in winter and three new bacterial types were locally isolated i.e. *Kluyvera cryocrescens*, *Pantoea agglomerans* and *Rahnella aquatilis*.

KEYWORDS: Tigris, Al-Zab, Bacterial indicators, Physicochemical parameters, Iraq.

INTRODUCTION

Fresh water bodies particularly rivers always considered as a main source of drinking and relevant human uses for maintenance of life. Water is essential to life and water pollution and the introduction of toxic substances to water bodies such as lakes, rivers, oceans, and so on,

getting dissolved in them, lying suspended in the water, or depositing on the bed,^[1,2] represents one of the most serious ecological threats.^[3] These natural water bodies usually under stress of environmental pollution including chemical, physical and biological aspects that might turn the nature of these waters to be risky for human beings uses.^[4,5] Environmental stress as well as human population growth associated with an increased industrial and civilian activities can all cause a damage for the natural water quality. These waters might be necessary for human needs which lead to continuous environmental survey and assessment to reveal the degree of pollution impact particularly on raw water sources like rivers, lakes, springs and deep wells waters i.e. ground waters.^[6] Raw water quality can be assessed using various parameters particularly the bacterial indicators of biological pollution.^[7] Moreover, the series of wars occurred in this country might increase the risk of water contamination that leads to public health hazards particularly the infectious diseases, cancers and genetic drifts.^[8,9,10] The present study aimed to investigate the bio-physicochemical parameters concerning pollution of River Tigris and Lower Al-Zab River of Iraq.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Description of the area studied

The collection site No.1 was located at the end of the River Al-Zab, Al-Hawija district, Kirkuk Governorate before the junction of Al-Zab with the River Tigris at the Maddallah fields. The other sites of water were located on River Tigris; site No.2 (Al-Shag area) and site No.3 (Al-Shjara area) were located on the River Tigris in Al-Hawija district, Kirkuk Governorate. The other five sites were located on River Tigris passing through the Salahaldeen Governorate from Al-Baiji to Samarra districts and they were; Al-Mazraa (S4), Tikrit University (S5), Tikrit Bridge (S6), Al-Oja (S7) and Abo-Dalaf (S8).

METHODS

Water sampling and parameters selected were carried out following Al-Jebouri and Edham.^[7]

RESULTS

Estimation of physicochemical parameters

The present study revealed a wide variation of different physical and chemical parameters assessed of raw and drinking waters under study. Temperature of air and waters of the sector studied were highly variables and the highest values were recorded among summer months which was almost 50 °C. Duncan statistical test did not show a significant difference

($P > 0.05$) for water temperature but air temperatures were significantly different ($P \leq 0.05$). Water turbidity, electrical conductivity, pH, dissolved oxygen values were changed with seasonal variations but they were statistically not different utilizing Duncan test and the P value was more than 0.05. The amounts of biological oxygen demand were statistically not different with the different months of study and the P value was more than 0.05 using Duncan test (Table 1, Figure 1). Correlation coefficient was 0.999 for different data set tested. R-squared of different variables was almost negligible i. e less than 0.001 which revealed a weak association between dependent and independent parameters.

Table 1: Estimated values of physicochemical parameters of raw and drinking waters.

Parameter	Raw water		Drinking water	
	Range	Mean	Range	Mean
Air Temperature ⁰ C	10.8 – 50.3	34	11.2-48.3	32
Water Temperature ⁰ C	10.2-23.7	17.8	9.6-25.3	17.4
Turbidity (NTU)	24.4-70.9	35.5	14.7-27.6	20.4
Electrical Conductivity (MS/Cm)	283.9-413.9	354.4	633.3-368	450.1
pH	7.6-8.6	8.1	7.8-8.3	8.1
Dissolved Oxygen (DO ₂)	7.44-9.7	8.6	9.7-7.3	8.5
Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD)	1.2-3.4	2.4	0.9--2	1.3

Figure 1: Regression analysis between raw and drinking water parameters. $r = 0.999$.

Distribution of bacterial indicators among raw and drinking waters

Table 2 shows that the total plate counts (total viable counts, TVC,s) of the raw waters were higher during winter but the same bacterial group numbers were highly present in drinking waters during summer months. Total coliforms and faecal coliforms numbers isolated were higher during summer from both raw and drinking waters. Statistical analyses did not show any significant differences using Duncan test ($P > 0.05$; Table 2, Figure 2). Correlation coefficient was 0.902 for different data set tested. R-squared of different variables was almost 0.5 which revealed a slight association between dependent and independent parameters.

Table 2: Distribution of bacterial indicators for pollution among raw waters of River Tigris and Lower Al-Zab River and drinking waters.

Bacterial Indicator	Raw Water		Drinking Water	
	Range	Average	Range	Average
Total plate count (TPC) (Cells/ cm ³)	51.1-111.3	79	6.7-90.7	22.1
Total Coliform bacteria (TCB)(Cells/ 100 cm ³)	395-1023.8	708-2	18-176.7	22.7
Faecal Coliforms (FC)(Cells/ 100 cm ³)	290.6-727.1	436.4	1.7-98.3	22.7

Figure 2: Regression analysis of bacterial indicators estimated in raw and drinking waters. $r = 0.903$.

Bacterial types isolated from raw and drinking water

The isolation frequency of *Enterobacteriaceae* from raw and drinking waters was 47.8 and 27.3 % respectively and the number of isolates of the same group was 22 and 3 from raw water and drinking waters respectively. Different types of *Vibrionaceae* were isolated at 9 and 3 occasions from raw and drinking waters through the period of study respectively. Other Gram-negative bacteria were also isolated and they were more dominant in raw waters compared to drinking waters (Table 3, Figure 3). The correlation coefficient was -0.044 which did not show a firm relation between different variable distribution. Figure 3 shows a variable R-squared of different data tested and its values ranged between 0.3 to 0.9.

Table 3: Bacterial types isolated from raw waters of River Tigris and Lower Al-Zab River and drinking water of the same water sources.

Bacterial type	Raw Water		Drinking Water	
	No.	%	No.	%
<i>Enterobacteriaceae</i>	22	47.8	3	27.3
<i>Vibrionaceae</i>	9	19.6	3	27.3
Other Gram-negative bacteria	15	32.6	5	45.4
Total	46	100	11	100

Figure 3: Regression analysis of bacterial types isolated from raw and drinking waters. r= 0.045.

New bacterial types

The present study revealed that *Kluyvera cryocrescens*, *Pantoea agglomerans* and *Rahnella aquatilis* bacterial types were locally isolated for first time.

DISCUSSION

Water pollution occurs when harmful substances contaminate fresh and marine water bodies such as, groundwater, rivers, lakes, and oceans rendering them unfavorable for various purposes such as drinking, recreation, and support to aquatic life. Over 80% of human-generated sewage is dumped untreated into rivers and oceans, causing pollution that causes over 50 diseases. In addition, poor water quality is linked to 80% of diseases globally.^[11] According to Taylor et al. progressive increases in industrialization, urbanization, and agricultural practices are the leading causes of water pollution. This alleviates the most common problem of eutrophication where inland waters and rivers are polluted with nitrogen and phosphorus runoff from fertilizers and the discharge of sewage and effluents.^[12] Domestic and industrial wastes outfalls causing a serious damage to human habitat and finally leading to various diseases as well as shortage in suitable water sources applicable for human consumption and other uses needed by mankind.^[4,8,11] River Tigris is usually under pressure of these environmental factors which cause its pollution.^[13,14] The Lower Al-Zab River is less affected by the mentioned factors due its geographical site that is almost relatively away from the civilian impact. Air temperature in Iraq is extreme which is highly elevated in summer exceeding 50°C but during winter might decreased to be less than -10°C. This thermal stress will obviously affect fauna and flora that associated in life with water bodies and their sources. Electrical conductivity can be defined as the ability of water to conduct the electric current and this character depends on the concentration of water ions contents and water temperature.^[15,16,17] Biological oxygen demand (BOD) can be used for evaluation of the level of pollution due to domestic as well as industrial wastes mixed with water bodies.^[7] This study systematically analyzed the impact of selected physicochemical as well as microbiological parameters on water pollution related to human health. From the point of view of limitations, this paper mainly focuses on the research of environmental pollution and science, and the research on chemical elements particularly heavy metals is less involved. Based on this, future research can strengthen research at tracing chemical levels. The present study revealed variable total viable counts of heterotrophic bacteria with respect to different sites and months of collection. The highest numbers were isolated during January, February and March i.e. during cold weather whereas the lowest number was seen during

September which is hot. Other workers concluded almost the same fluctuation of total viable counts in Iraqi rivers.^[4,15] Moreover, the series of wars occurred in this country might increased the risk of water contamination that leads to public health hazards particularly the infectious diseases, cancers and genetic drifts.^[18,19,20] Finally, further investigations are desperately needed to explore the various changes that might occurred in this locality.

CONCLUSIONS

The highest degree of water pollution was seen during January of the year. The purification technology and management for drinking water stations studied were inefficient that some of the samples tested were not acceptable for human consumption according to international standards of drinking water quality. The water bodies of River Tigris and lower Al-Zab river were under risk of domestic outfalls, which led to dominance of Enterobacteriaceae and other human – derived bacteria in these natural waters. The present study revealed that *Kluyvera cryocrescens*, *Pantoea agglomerans* and *Rahnella aquatilis* bacterial types were locally isolated for first.

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Competing interests

The author declare that he has no competing interests.

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